

A Study on Instagram as an Effective Digital Marketing Tool

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ABSTRACT

Instagram is a social media platform for people to share photos and videos this opportunity for businesses and experts to use this platform for marketing their products and services. This helps the public to be aware of the sufficient options that are available in the market to purchase a product and service. This also enables business concerns to analyze the reach of a product/service in the market. The study on this marketing tool aims on scattering the importance of Instagram as a digital marketing tool in every organization. It is one of the significant marketing tools that allow businesses to communicate. The ultimate of this research is to create brand awareness of the growing business concerns. And also is to create reputation management, getting customers, getting potential clients, and more. Interview and questionnaire are the methodologies that will be used to complete this study. Primary and secondary data such as journals and articles have been used in this study.

INTRODUCTION

Instagram founded in 2010 for entertainment purpose for sharing photos and videos to their followers. Instagram added few functions like sending direct message, feeding post, reels, posting photos; posting videos etc... it has a option to create 15 sec of video called reels which enable to gain multiple number of followers. This concept went viral among youngsters and celebrity in connecting people. This popularity became the trend over a period which brought in paid promotions. Social network marketing is a popular marketing strategy for many companies. As now a day people are more into social media and social networking, people unlike the past traditional marketing strategies such as news paper advertisement, commercials and televisions do not give much impact to the customers these days. People these days are attracted to online marketing. Looking at the opportunities gained through social media to interact with potential customers, social networking sites have been a hot issue for the marketers. Nowadays Instagram place a vital role in online marketing system.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

According to [Durianto, D., Sugiarto.Anton.Dan S, Hendrawan. (2003)], the effectiveness of advertising can be seen from two points of view of the results / impact, namely: the impact of communication from an advertisement that effects on attentiveness, familiarity, and preference, and the second is the impact on sales, where this impact is more difficult to measure because sales are influenced by many factors not only by advertising. Following Shimp, T., and Andrews, J. C. (2013)] some criteria to make an ad considered effective are: 1) Ad is a manifestation of marketing strategy; 2) An effective ad derived from consumer's perspectives. It should be made based on consumers' predetermined value and longing, not merely based on marketers' needs; 3) Ads may find unique ways to pierce explosive

advertising; 4) Effective advertisement does not promise anything that cannot be done; and 5) Prevent creative ideas derived from unclear strategies.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The emergence of evolving path of purchase leads to gaining a clear understanding of revolutionized digital channels. From the basic essential to everything is available online so that the customer can purchase it from home. This study investigates about Instagram as an effective digital marketing tool. The study presence detail analysis of semi-structure interviews and questions. "ENTERTAINMENT" is the key for the marketers used to promote their product, which enable the Instagram users to know the product option and information in the form of entertainment.

The objectives are as follows:

- To analyze the effectiveness of Instagram as digital marketing tool.
- To evaluate the use of Instagram by consumers.
- To analyze the awareness of Instagram
- To understand Instagram as informative rather than entertaining.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Are People using Instagram for online shopping?
2. Which age group people are using Instagram for online shopping?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the study on “Instagram as an effective digital marketing tool” Primary data i.e survey method was used by circulating Google form in a total of 150 respondent of these participants only 129 was taken for analysis as those with missing data those did not meet the experimental conditions were excluded. And the research was also done through interview method with 12 people who spend an average of 3 to 5 minutes those where the people who spend an average of 30 to 40 minutes on Instagram a day. The study is been analyzed with the use of Chi square.

LIMITATIONS

It is Important to note that this study several limitations, that could also have important implications for the result of this study. One of the major limitations is the sample size. Although a total 124 participants were recruited for this study, only 100 participants were taken into analyses. This may also explain why almost no significant effects were found in this study.

FINDINGS

The fact that no significant effect where founded between the advertising conditions and the depended variable, may be due to the factor that these depended variable are not so relevant to advertising on Instagram.

A final limitation of this study was the fact that no pre-tests were done on participants already ad existing believes or attitude towards the digital marketing, marketing tools, Instagram.

Future studies should do pre-tests on whether or not the topic or relevant to the participants, as this may have implications on the research results.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To test whether or not Instagram advertisements let to an effective digital marketing strategy in according to their age categories, a chi-square was conducted. A chi-square test is a statistical test used to compare observed results with expected results. The purpose of this test is to determine if a difference between observed data and expected data is due to chance, or if it is due to a relationship between the variables you are studying.

Based on the survey through Google forms it was determined that 28% of 10-17 age group users use Instagram for their online shopping 60% of 18-25 age group users use Instagram for their online shopping & 12% of 25-45 age group users use Instagram for their online shopping.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where,

H₀= the proportion of Instagram online shopping users with the age of 10-17, 18-25 & 26-45 are 0.28, 0.60 & 0.12 respectively.

H₁= the proportion of Instagram online shopping users with the age of 10-17, 18-25 & 26-45 does not match the proposed model.

Age	O _i	E _i	O _i -E _i	(O-E) ²
10-17	38	36.1	1.9	3.61
18-25	73	77.4	-4.4	19.36
26-45	18	15.5	2.5	6.25
total	129			0.7533

Using the table, the critical value for a 0.05 significance level with df = 2 is 5.99

This means that 95 times out of 100, a survey that agrees with a sample will have a χ^2 value of 5.99 or less.

The Chi-square statistic is only 0.7533, so this accepts the null hypothesis.

Therefore, the proportion of Instagram online shopping users with the age of 10-17, 18-25 & 26-45 are 0.28, 0.60 & 0.12 respectively.

Conclusion:

The effectively of Instagram as digital marketing is declared effective. This is based on the results of calculations on Instagram users and Instagram Ad influencers based on the age category showed effective results. However the different case studies also show that the Instagram marketing developed the opportunities of growth in their business. The

effectiveness of our study as an overall Instagram in an effective way of digital marketing strategies tool which enhance and create opportunities to grow in business. This shows that Instagram is the on growing business to create opportunities to grow. This effectiveness is based on the users and advertisement influencers on basic of age categories.

REFERENCE

1. Cox, Shirley A. (2010). "Online Social Network Member Attitude toward Online Advertising Formats." MA thesis, The Rochester Institute of Technology.
2. Brain Dean (2022) "Instagram demographic Statistics: How many people use Instagram in 2022"
3. Durianto, D., Sugiarto., Anton., dan S, Hendrawan. (2003). Invasi Pasar Dengan.